

Antioxidant and other beneficent effects of free and conjugated phytosteroids of *Solanum* and *Withania*[†]

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Abstract : Antioxidant capacity of an array of free and conjugated phytosteroids of *Solanum xanthocarpum* and *Solanum nigrum*, and withasteroids of *Withania somnifera* has been assessed. Four standard sets of assays, namely, reduction of ABTS, DPPH, FRAP and superoxide radical, have been used. The contribution, in this regard, of metal ions, naturally-complexed with the phytosteroids and withasteroids, has also been evaluated. The findings suggest the contribution of naturally occurring metallo-organic complexes in human well being. The mechanisms suggested for the antioxidant actions of the compounds project the role of molecular architecture of free and conjugated steroids. Some other beneficent actions of these compounds, e.g. systemic lowering of cholesterol and LDL, and the selective inhibition of COX-2 by sitoindoside-indolealkylamine-conjugated withasteroids, are noteworthy. The last-named compound(s) contribute also to the adaptogenic activity of *W. somnifera*.

Keywords : *Solanum*, *Withania*, phytosteroids, withasteroid-indolealkylamine, metal ion conjugates, antioxidant capacity, adaptogen.

Introduction

Two broad groups of steroids that occur in nature are phytosteroids, produced essentially by plants and zoosteroids, produced by animals, including human beings. Among these two broad groups, there exist many biologically active natural steroid intermediates¹ and also their conjugates², formed in the milieu of the total plant extracts, with oligosaccharides, lipids, proteins and complexed/chelated metal ions. Phyto- and zoo-steroids elicit remarkably different types of bioactivities associated with health and diseases of mankind. Many of the disease states result from the systemic oxidant-antioxidant imbalance. Oxidants and antioxidants have well defined functions in plant and animal organisms and reside in specific compartments. An imbalance between the two results in many patho-physiological changes in human beings. For example, ultraviolet-B (UV-B) radiation that initiates lipid peroxidation and generates hydroxyl radical has been shown to induce these effects via generation of superoxide radical. Its attack on ferritin results in release and mobilization of free iron ions. Furthermore,

superoxide radical, in turn, can react to produce hydrogen peroxide which again restarts the Fenton reaction³.

The augmentation of the collective anti-oxidant enzymes, superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and glutathione peroxidase (GPX), by certain withasteroids, was reported in an earlier study⁴. In the present study, the antioxidant capacity of free and conjugated phytosteroids of two *Solanum* species, viz. *S. xanthocarpum* and *S. nigrum*; and one *Withania* species, viz. *W. somnifera*, was investigated following the principles of hydrogen atom transfer (HAT) and electron transfer (ET) assays^{5,6}. Increased generation of oxidative free radicals or impaired antioxidant defense mechanisms have been implicated in many debilitating states of human beings, e.g. the complications in the aging process, neurodegenerative conditions including Parkinsonism and Alzheimers's disease, in chronic stress induced perturbed homeostasis including immuno-depression, in inflammation and other diseased conditions⁷. The distinctly positive observations and their mechanistic rationale resulting from this investigation would lend credence to the health claims in respect

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

of these plants mentioned in the Ayurveda.

Results and discussion

The sterols, steroidal sapogenins and steroidal glycoalkaloids of *S. xanthocarpum* and *S. nigrum* are reported in Table 1 with their respective yields.

Likewise, the list of withanolide aglycones, withanolide glycosides, and withanolide-indolealkylamine conjugates of *Withania somnifera*, with their respective yields, are reported in Table 2.

The total extractives of *S. xanthocarpum* and *S. nigrum* comprising of sterols, steroidal sapogenins and steroidal glycoalkaloids as given in Table 1 were tested for antioxidant activity. This was carried out before and after passing through a strong cation exchange resin Dowex 50/H⁺ for separation of chelated/complexed metal ions from the steroidal entities. Four accepted *in vitro* hydrogen atom transfer (HAT) and electron transfer (ET) assay systems were employed. These are, 2,2'-Azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS) radical cat-

Table 1. Phytosteroids^a of *Solanum* species and their yields^b

Name of the species	Phytosterols	Sapogenins	Glycoalkaloids
<i>S. xanthocarpum</i>	β-Sitosterol ³³ , Carpesterol ³⁴ , Norcarpesterol ³⁴ 0.5–0.9 ^b	Diosgenin ^{33,34} 0.4–0.8 ^b	Solasodine (2), Solasonine (3), Solamargine(4) ^{33,35} 0.4–0.9 ^b
<i>S. nigrum</i>	β-Sitosterol, Stigmasterol, Campesterol 0.0001–0.0005 ^b	Diosgenin, Tigogenin, Degalactotigogenin ^{37,38} 0.5–0.8 ^b	Solasodine (2), Solasonine (3), Solamargine (4), Tomatidenol (1) ^{37–39} 0.4–0.9 ^b

^aStructure nos. are given in parenthesis.

^bYield in % (w/w) of total plant extract.

Table 2. Withanolide aglycones, withanolide glycosides and withanolide-indolealkylamine-conjugates^a present in *Withania somnifera*

Name of the species	Withanolide aglycones	Withanolide glycoside	Withanolide-indolealkylamine-conjugates ²⁶
<i>W. somnifera</i> (cultivated variety)	Withaferin A (6) ^{40,41} 0.4–0.7 ^b	Sitoindosides (6,7) ^{40,41} 12.5–16.5 ^b	8, 9 0.01–0.02 ^b

^aStructure nos. are given in parenthesis.

^bYield in % (w/w) of total plant extract.

Table 3. Antioxidant assays of steroids of *S. xanthocarpum* and *S. nigrum* with and without metal ion conjugation

Samples	Assay methods			
	DPPH assay	ABTS assay	FRAP assay	Superoxide assay
IC ₅₀ values in µg/ml				
<i>S. xanthocarpum</i> (total steroidal extractives) (see Experimental)	55.59 ± 0.42	18.83 ± 0.08	19.68 ± 0.17	256.02 ± 2.25
<i>S. xanthocarpum</i> Dowex 50/H ⁺ eluted extract	81.17 ± 1.20	20.11 ± 0.25	13.99 ± 0.26	68.48 ± 17.16
<i>S. nigrum</i> (total steroidal extractives)	104.09 ± 1.62	26.43 ± 0.28	22.69 ± 0.20	309.97 ± 9.15
<i>S. nigrum</i> Dowex 50/H ⁺ eluted extract	124.65 ± 1.90	27.59 ± 0.27	17.49 ± 0.16	623.22 ± 13.57

Data represented as mean ±SD; n = 4.

Table 4. Antioxidant assays of withasteroids of *Withania somnifera* with and without metal ion conjugation

Samples	Assay methods			
	DPPH assay	ABTS assay	FRAP assay	Superoxide assay
	IC ₅₀ values in µg/ml			
<i>W. somnifera</i> (total withasteroidal extractives) (see Experimental)	241.59 ± 2.99	30.05 ± 0.241	50.55 ± 0.69	615.57 ± 17.72
<i>W. somnifera</i> Dowex 50/H ⁺ eluted extract	401.25 ± 3.33	36.25 ± 0.18	46.45 ± 0.52	776.33 ± 28.26

Data represented as mean ±SD; n = 4.

ion decolorisation assay^{5,8,9}, 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical decolorisation assay^{5,10,11}, Ferric Ion Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) assay^{5,10,12} and superoxide radical scavenging assay by NBT (nitro blue tetrazolium)-NADH (nicotinamide adenine di nucleotide reduced)-PMS (phenazonium methosulphate) method^{5,10}. The IC₅₀ values are incorporated in Table 3.

Likewise, the total withasteroid extractives of *Withania somnifera* comprising of withanolide aglycones, withanolide glycosides and withanolide-indolealkylamine conjugates in the proportion given in Table 2 were subjected to same assay procedures, as mentioned above, before and after passing through Dowex 50/H⁺. The IC₅₀ values are incorporated in Table 4.

In order to allocate the contribution of the sterols,

Table 5. Antioxidant assays of an individual sterol and sapogenin of *S. xanthocarpum* and *S. nigrum*

Samples	DPPH assay IC ₅₀ values in µg/ml
β-Sitosterol	3.02±0.15
Diosgenin	3.26±0.32

Data represented as mean ±SD; n = 4.

steroidal sapogenins and steroidal glycoalkaloids to the total antioxidant capacity of *S. xanthocarpum* and *S. nigrum*, before and after passing through Dowex 50/H⁺ resin, the different entities were separately assayed and the results are incorporated in Tables 5 and 6.

Glycoalkaloid fraction was isolated from *S. xanthocarpum*. This fraction was also passed through Dowex 50/H⁺ and subjected to antioxidant assays.

The details of the metal ions differently complexed with the compounds stated in Table 1 are reported in Tables 7 and 8 along with their respective amounts.

The metal ions associated with the steroidal glycoalkaloid fraction of *S. xanthocarpum* are incorporated in Table 9.

The metal ions differently complexed with compounds stated in Table 2 are reported in Table 10 along with their respective amounts.

The phytosteroids of different structural categories of the *Solanum* and *Withania* species exhibited antioxidant activity, albeit differently, in the four standard assay systems^{5,8-12}. The results are incorporated in Tables 3 to 6.

Table 6. Antioxidant assay of steroidal glycoalkaloids of *S. xanthocarpum* with and without metal ion conjugation

Samples	Assay methods			
	DPPH assay	ABTS assay	FRAP assay	Superoxide assay
	IC ₅₀ values in µg/ml			
<i>S. xanthocarpum</i> / glycoalkaloid	100.38 ± 2.43	20.49 ± 0.5	29.80 ± 0.54	554.79 ± 33.94
<i>S. xanthocarpum</i> / glycoalkaloid Dowex 50/H ⁺ eluted	235.4 ± 3.16	40.62 ± 4.56	28.87 ± 0.44	703.04 ± 14.0

Data represented as mean ±SD; n = 4.

Table 7. Estimation of total, Dowex eluted and retarded metal ions present in the extractives of *S. xanthocarpum*

Samples	Total %							
	Fe	Ca	Mg	Cu	Zn	Pb	Cd	Hg
Total extract	0.0147 ± 0.0059	0.188 ± 0.009	0.565 ± 0.017	<0.0001	0.012 ± 0.004	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001
Resin-eluted fraction	0.0005 ± 0.002	0.0016 ± 0.006	0.003 ± 0.0012	<0.0001	0.002 ± 0.001	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001
Resin-retarded fraction	0.014 ± 0.001	0.179 ± 0.011	0.561 ± 0.005	<0.0001	0.0094 ± 0.001	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001

Data represented as mean ±SD; n = 4.

Note that, chelated/complexed metal ions are largely arrested by cation exchange resin and the occurrence of negligible extent of heavy metal ions in the natural extract.

Table 8. Estimation of total, Dowex eluted and retarded metal ions present in the extractives of *S. nigrum*

Samples	Total %							
	Fe	Ca	Mg	Cu	Zn	Pb	Cd	Hg
Total extract	0.105 ± 0.004	0.360 ± 0.02	0.014 ± 0.001	<0.0001	0.11 ± 0.02	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001
Resin-eluted fraction	0.015 ± 0.001	0.030 ± 0.004	0.002 ± 0.0004	<0.0001	0.014 ± 0.005	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001
Resin-retarded fraction	0.080 ± 0.005	0.31 ± 0.01	0.012 ± 0.0003	<0.0001	0.094 ± 0.006	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001

Data represented as mean ±SD; n = 4.

Note that, chelated/complexed metal ions are largely arrested by cation exchange resin and the occurrence of negligible extent of heavy metal ions in the natural extract.

Table 9. Estimation of total, Dowex eluted and retarded metal ions present in the steroidal glycoalkaloids of *S. xanthocarpum*

Samples	Total %							
	Fe	Ca	Mg	Cu	Zn	Pb	Cd	Hg
Total extract	0.0125 ± 0.001	0.192 ± 0.02	0.584 ± 0.04	<0.0001	0.09 ± 0.0001	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001
Resin-eluted fraction	0.003 ± 0.0004	0.004 ± 0.001	0.023 ± 0.08	<0.0001	0.01 ± 0.0001	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001
Resin-retarded fraction	0.0121 ± 0.001	0.187 ± 0.01	0.558 ± 0.04	<0.0001	0.07 ± 0.0001	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001

Data represented as mean ±SD; n = 4.

Note that, chelated/complexed metal ions are largely arrested by cation exchange resin and the occurrence of negligible extent of heavy metal ions in the natural extract.

The solubility of the compounds and some other characteristics, e.g. micellar assembly and metal ion complexation, produced considerable differences in the ex-

tent of antioxidant capacity.

The following mechanisms (Schemes 1-3) for the antioxidant actions of the phytosteroids against ABTS, DPPH

Table 10. Estimation of total, Dowex eluted and retarded metal ions present in the extractives of *W. somnifera*

Samples	Total %							
	Fe	Ca	Mg	Cu	Zn	Pb	Cd	Hg
Total extract	0.0061 ± 0.002	0.16 ± 0.015	0.095 ± 0.008	0.0015 ± 0.001	0.0105 ± 0.003	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001
Resin-eluted fraction	0.0011 ± 0.0001	0.045 ± 0.003	0.026 ± 0.004	<0.0001	0.0023 ± 0.0001	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001
Resin-retarded fraction	0.0048 ± 0.0015	0.104 ± 0.003	0.065 ± 0.006	0.0014 ± 0.0002	0.008 ± 0.001	<0.0005	<0.0001	<0.0001

Data represented as mean ±SD; n = 4.

Note that, chelated/complexed metal ions are largely arrested by cation exchange resin and the occurrence of negligible extent of heavy metal ions in the natural extract.

and FRAP, respectively, are envisaged.

The process of generation of resonance stabilized allylic radical from the phytosterols (11 and 12, Scheme 1) provides the reductant. A similar sequence of hydrogen abstraction and electron addition seems to be involved in the reduction of DPPH (15, Scheme 2), FRAP (17, Scheme

3) and $O_2^{\cdot-}$ radical ion.

The FRAP values obtained in this study (Tables 3, 4 and 6) indicating the efficiency of the reduction process by the phytosteroids and withasteroids have the contribution also of reduced metallo-complexed steroidal glycoalkaloid in the *Solanum* sp. (Schemes 1-3) and

Scheme 1. Mechanism of reduction of $\text{ABTS}^{\cdot+}$ by phytosterols (and equivalents).

Scheme 2. Mechanism of reduction of DPPH-radicals by phytosterols.

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FRAP : $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}} (\text{TPTZ})_2\text{Cl}_3$

(TPTZ = 2,4,6-tripyridyl-*s*-triazine,

as ligands L1) 17

The electron (e^-) has resulted from the generation of resonance stabilized styryl-allyl radical. An additional site of action involving C_{27} hydroxy fraction and metal ions constitutes structure (21). This explains the significance of withaferin A, in small amounts, to exhibit the antistress adaptogenic activity of *Withania somnifera* by withasteroids including sitoindosides (IX, X and XV) (6 and 7) and withanolide-indolealkylamine conjugates (8 and 9).

21

L_2 = Withasteroid ligand

19

20

Scheme 3. Mechanism of reduction of FRAP by withasteroids (with or without metal ion-bonded antioxidants).

withasteroids in the *Withania* sp. (Schemes 1–3). A fast electron transfer process from the withasteroid [Fe^{II}]-complex (19, Scheme 3) and also from spirosta saponins/glycoalkaloids to the oxidant species (DPPH, ABTS, FRAP and $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$) seems to be responsible for the antioxidant capacity of the metal ion conjugated total extracts. Values are given in Tables 3–6.

Mg^{2+} ion complexation of the *Solanum* glycoalkaloid (s) (5; Fig. 4) would result in the formation of micellar assembly in solution. This would confer stability to the resultant incipient aminium radical species (22, Scheme 4) generated from the antioxidant action. Delocalisation of the electron throughout the micellar structure (23a, Scheme 4; Fig. 4) would result in a number of consequences, e.g. stability of the antioxidant entity and consequent H transfer from the enamine.

Aside from the antioxidant functions of the phytosteroids and their attendant beneficent effects in human health, the potent cholesterol and LDL-lowering effects of these compounds make them attractive candidates for human nutrition and well being.

As early as the 1950s, plant derived sterols were reported to decrease serum cholesterol levels in mammals¹³. The observation was soon confirmed^{14–16}. The decreased blood cholesterol levels by phytosterols are attributable, at least in part, to an inhibition of cholesterol absorption from the digestive tract¹⁷. The inhibition was ascribed to involve a number of mechanisms, including partitioning in the micellar phase of the intestinal lumen, presence in the unstirred water layer or other mucosa barriers that might limit transmembrane transport and alteration in the rates of cholesterol esterification in the intestinal wall^{18–20}.

6

Withaferin A: R=H
Sitoindoside-IX: R= D-glucoside

Sitoindoside-X: R= 6-O-palmitoyl
D-glucose

7

Sitoindoside XV
R= Oligosaccharide= Linear glucose, Where
n= 2 to 6.

8

Withanolide-indolealkylamine conjugates

9

Fig. 2. Bioactive compounds of *Withania somnifera*.

cholesterolemic effect²⁷.

Phytosteroid glycosides and acyl steryl glycosides, e.g. the sitoindosides (IX, X, XV) of the *Withania somnifera* and spirosta saponins/glycoalkaloids of the abovementioned *Solanum* species lower intestinal absorption of cholesterol.

The application of sitoindosides as potent adaptogens,

and antioxidant and antistress agents is well documented²⁴. Furthermore, sitoindosides -IX (6)²⁵, -X (6), -XV (7)²⁵-serotonin conjugates (8 and 9) hold significant potential as selective cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2)-enzyme inhibitors. Such enzyme-inhibitory action of withanolide-conjugates had precedent in the literature²⁶.

COX-2 – prostaglandin synthase-2, has been detected

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 3. 3D-structure of steroidal glycoalkaloids of *Solanum* sp. showing an intermingling of the hydrophobic and hydrophilic components. This intermingling results in a severe cell-membrane perturbation and eventual cellular toxicity. Magnesium ion complexation (white ball) of the steroidal glycoalkaloid (Fig. 4) has produced a micellar (amphiphilic) structure thereby facilitates smooth entry of magnesium via the cell membrane. This lipoidal complex compound acts as a strong neuroprotective agent.

Scheme 4. Mechanism of antioxidant action of Mg^{2+} -glycoalkaloid complex of *Solanum* sp.

in many cells, e.g. macrophages when the gene encoding has been expressed. Effective stimuli for such expression include PAF, IL-1 and lipopolysaccharide. The COX-2 inhibitory action of the *Ashwagandha* Sitoindosides (and equivalents) would seem to be mediated by the regulation of the COX-2 stimuli factors. COX-1, also known as the prostaglandin G/H synthase-1, is needed for certain normal cell functions. Hence, selective COX-2 inhibition might be efficacious without the adverse side effects, e.g. renal damage and gastric ulceration, commonly seen with drugs, such as aspirin and indomethacin, which inhibit both COX-1 and COX-2.

The sitoindoside-serotonin conjugates (8 and 9) were isolated from fruits, leaf-buds and 1-2 week-old leaves of *W. somnifera* of a specific chemotype¹. The structures of

these two conjugates were derived from comprehensive chromatographic and spectroscopic analyses and selective degradation. Briefly, the two components, sitoindoside and serotonin, were disentangled by selective dissociation, and characterized by HPLC using markers. The specific COX-2 inhibitory action of the serotonin-sitoindosides and sitoindosides (IX, X, XV), *per se*, if meaningfully exploited, may find significant application as anti inflammatory agents (via inhibition of selective prostaglandin synthesis). This would provide advantage over non-selective, non-steroidal anti inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). The serotonin-sitoindoside conjugates are two new additions of the bioactive principles of *W. somnifera* of significant reckoning. Work in this direction is in progress.

Experimental

Samples and techniques : Authenticated plant materials, viz. *Solanum xanthocarpum*, *Solanum nigrum* and *Withania somnifera*, were obtained from Indian Herbs Ltd., Saharanpur (U.P.). All the chemicals and reagents are of A.R. grade, standard α -solanine, α -chaconine, β -sitosterol, diosgenin, 2,2'-Azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt (ABTS), 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), 2,4,6-Tri(2-pyridyl)-s-triazine (TPTZ) and Dowex 50WX8-100 were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals, St. Lewis. Iron(III) chloride, nicotinamide adenine di nucleotide reduced (NADH), nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT), phenazonium methosulphate (PMS) and were obtained from Merck (India).

Reagents : The following spray reagents were used – Carr-Price spray reagent²⁷ (for steroidal glycoalkaloid) : 20% antimony(III) chloride in acetic acid and dichloromethane (1 : 3). Anisaldehyde reagent²⁸ (for sterols) : 10 ml glacial acetic acid is added to 0.4 ml anisaldehyde, followed by addition of 85 ml methanol and 5 ml concentrated H₂SO₄. This solution was prepared 2 h before use.

Isolation of phyto- and withasteroids : Dried and powdered plant materials (whole plant) of the two *Solanum* species were hot extracted (2 h) with aqueous-methanol (40 : 60). The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. Sterols were extracted by following a published procedure²⁹. The extractives were analyzed by HPTLC using markers. Water was used as the solvent of extraction for *W. somnifera* (whole plant). The hot extraction was continued for 2 h and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The total extractives were subjected to detail HPTLC and HPLC analyses using authentic markers.

Isolation of glycoalkaloids : Steroidal glycoalkaloids of *Solanum* species were isolated as follows. The plant materials were hot extracted with methanol-acetic acid (95 : 5). The methanol solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The aqueous part was washed with chloroform and neutralized by sodium bicarbonate. The liberated glycoalkaloids were extracted by *n*-butanol and subjected to HPTLC analyses using authentic markers.

HPTLC : CAMAG assembly, equipped with Linomat TLC applicator and Scanner 3. Instrument and data processing were monitored by WinCATs software 1.3.4.

HPTLC of sterols of *Solanum* : Plate, silica gel 60F₂₅₄/

Merck; mobile phase, toluene-ethyl acetate-acetic acid (15 : 4 : 1); spray reagent, anisaldehyde reagent; densitometric determination at 525 nm.

HPTLC of steroidal glycoalkaloid of *Solanum* : Plate, silica gel 60F₂₅₄/Merck; mobile phase-solvent-1, butanol-acetone-acetic acid-water (35 : 35 : 10 : 20); solvent-2, chloroform-methanol (50 : 50); spray reagent, Carr-Price reagent; densitometric determination at 550 nm.

HPLC : WATERS assembly, equipped with PDA detector (WATERS 2996), pump (WATERS 516), injector (Rheodyne 7725i).

HPLC of withasteroids of *W. somnifera* : Column, Merck-Hiber® pre-packed column RT 250-4, 4 × 250 mm cartridge column, with a reverse guard column; solvent, acetonitrile-water (1 : 1); flow rate, 0.6 ml/min; run time, 20 min; injection volume 20 μ L with loop injector; detection at 225 nm.

AAS : GBC-AWANTA system; standard CRMs are obtained from MERCK-India.

Antioxidant assays :

2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical (DPPH) scavenging capacity assay^{5,10,11} :

DPPH is one of a few stable and commercially available organic nitrogen radicals and has a UV-Vis absorption maximum at λ 517 nm. Upon reduction, the solution color fades. The DPPH assay is typically run by the following procedure. DPPH solution (3 mg in 25 ml ethanol) was mixed with sample solution (0.1 mL). The absorbance of the mixture during the reaction progress was monitored at λ 517 nm for 20 min or until the absorbance was stable. Upon reduction, the colour of the solution fades. The concentration that causes a decrease in the initial DPPH concentration by 50% is defined as IC₅₀.

ABTS cation radical decolourisation assay^{5,8,9} :

ABTS-, the oxidant, was generated by persulfate oxidation of 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS²⁻). This solution was diluted with phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) until the absorbance reached 0.7 to 0.8 at λ 734 nm. One ml of the resulting solution was mixed with the sample. The absorbance was read at 30 °C, 4 min after mixing at 30 °C. The difference of the absorbance reading was plotted versus the antioxidant concentrations to give a straight line. The concentration that caused a decrease in the initial ABTS concentration by 50% is defined as IC₅₀.

Ferric ion reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay^{5,10,12} :

The oxidant in the FRAP assay was prepared by mixing TPTZ, acetate buffer and FeCl₃·H₂O. The conglomerate is referred to as "FRAP reagent". The final solution has Fe^{III} of 1.67 mM and TPTZ of 0.83 mM concentration. To measure FRAP value, 300 μL of freshly prepared FRAP reagent was warmed to 37 °C and a reagent blank reading was taken at λ 593 nm, then sample and

30 μL of water are added. Absorbance readings were taken at λ 593 nm. The concentration that caused an increase in the initial FRAP concentration by 50% is defined as IC₅₀.

O₂^{•-} scavenging capacity assay^{5,10} :

This assay was conducted following a published procedure. Briefly, using NADH-phenazine methosulphate-O₂ as the O₂^{•-} generator and nitroblue tatrazolum as the probe. The absorbance were measured at λ 540 nm and IC₅₀ value calculated in the usual way.

^afor *Solanum* sp., ^bfor *Withania* sp.

^c500 °C for 2.5 h.

^dFe ions measured by 1,10-orthophenanthroline³⁰.

^eCa and Mg ions measured by complexometric (EDTA) titration³¹.

^fCu, Zn, Pb, Cd, Hg by AAS³².

^gDetermination of ligands by chromatography (HPTLC, HPLC).

Scheme 5. A general method for sample preparation and estimation of metal ions in *Solanum* and *Withania* sp.

Sample preparation for conjugated and free metal ion estimation :

A general method for this experiment is given in Scheme 5.

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